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A conceptual framework for responding to cross-border climate change impacts

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Abstract

Climate change adaptation is most often defined as a local and national governance issue. While the scientific literature recognizes the potential significance of cross-border climate impacts and new methods are being developed for the assessment of risks and opportunities associated with them, adaptation planning approaches are mostly confined within tightly defined sectoral contexts or specific geographical regions. These approaches overlook transmission of impacts across sectors and borders and fail to lay the groundwork for systemic responses and cross-scale solutions for adaptation and resilience building. We propose a conceptual framework for identifying and filtering different types of responses to cross-border climate impacts. The framework provides typologies of cross-border climate impacts and responses to them and define actor constellations who may respond to impacts. Analysing targets and dynamics of different response types, a set of governance modalities are then proposed which may be appropriate to adequately address certain impact types. A key to suitable governance modalities is a recognition of response effects and undesirable consequences that may redistribute or exacerbate risks across scales. The response framework can be used to assess the appropriateness of existing responses to cross-border climate impacts and help designing and implementing adequate responses to future cascading risks and opportunities. To illustrate these potential uses, we apply the framework to a historical example, the food affordability crisis in 2010, and a hypothetical future-oriented case, the global food security crisis. The framework captures the transmission of impacts and responses and provides a sequence of steps to investigate the suitability of historical responses to cross-border climate impacts and map policy gaps and under-represented response types. It also presents a structured architecture for identifying suitable responses and governance modalities for addressing cascading climate risks and opportunities and potentially minimising undesirable consequences of adaptation actions.

Graphical abstract

Keywords

Cross-border climate impacts; Cascading climate risks; Adaptation; Impact transmission system; Response transmission system; Policy simulation

1. Introduction

Climate change impacts can transmit across interdependent systems. Such impacts can propagate across both sectors (Abe, 2014; Becker et al., 2013; Goldstein et al., 2019; Haraguchi and Lall, 2015; Koks et al., 2019), and across regional, national and sub-national borders through various pathways that include financial flows, trade networks, and movements of people (Benzie et al., 2019; Challinor et al., 2016; Hedlund et al., 2018a). Therefore, there is an urgent need for further research to provide a scientific basis on how risks and opportunities resulting from these impacts can be addressed.

The importance of interconnections across interdependent systems is recognized in various fields. Defence and security studies highlight the risks (e.g. cyber) of transmission of impacts across political borders and geographic locations (Ermoliev and Winterfeldt, 2012; Sommer and Brown, 2011; Ullrich and Kamp, 2021). Cross-border links between financial institutions, such as banks, have been identified as being particularly vulnerable to the transmission of impacts and subject to potential crises cascading between remote locations (Aldasoro et al., 2020; Bricco and Xu, 2019; Gai and Kapadia, 2019). Further studies have looked at disruptions to global trade and supply chains through the lens of systemic risks from climatic (Abe, 2014; Haraguchi and Lall, 2015; Knittel et al., 2020) and non-climatic (Ghadge et al., 2020; Osadchiy et al., 2016; Scheibe and Blackhurst, 2018) events. Food (de Raymond et al., 2021) and water security (Munia et al., 2020) are also prominent among other thematic areas in which attention has been drawn to the propagation of risks across borders.

The risk and risk governance literature uses the concept of systemic risk to refer to certain types of risks characterized by high levels of connectivity, uncertainty and ambiguity, and non-linearity in linkages and relationships (Marie-Valentine and Thomas, 2018; Renn, 2016; Renn et al., 2019; Schweizer and Renn, 2019). Systemic risks are defined as those that cascade through multiple system components and interconnected sub-systems and can trigger large-scale changes and/or threats to the system as a whole (Challinor et al., 2018; Helbing, 2013). When the concept of systemic risk is applied in climate change research, studies particularly focus on cross-border and cascading risks induced by climate-related impacts (Choudhury, 2021; Hui-Min et al., 2021).

Despite the growing body of literature on cross-border climate change impacts¹ (Benzie et al., 2019; Carter et al., 2021; Challinor et al., 2018; Hedlund et al., 2018b; Prabhakar and Rama, 2022), and recognition of associated risks and opportunities as a major and underexplored phenomenon in a number of national and regional risk assessments (Challinor et al., 2016; European Commission, 2018; Leitner et al., 2020; Liverman, 2016; Lung et al., 2017; Okano et al., 2022; Sentance and Betts, 2012; Smith et al., 2018; UK Foresight, 2011; Vonk et al., 2015), research on approaches to address and adapt to these types of impact is still limited (e.g., Talebian et al., 2021; Zscheischler et al., 2018). While adaptation is increasingly being seen as a global challenge which requires regional, international, and transboundary governance (Dzebo and Stripple, 2015; Persson, 2019), no study yet exists to provide a framework for systematically identifying and categorizing different types of responses to cross-border climate impacts across scales.

We develop a framework to help understand different response types and governance modalities to address different types of cross-border climate impacts. The main objective of this paper is to describe specific cross-border climate impacts and to hypothesise the suitability of multiple ‘stylised’ response

¹ Henceforth abbreviated to “cross-border climate impacts”

types for each type of impact. We propose a set of governance modalities that may then be analysed for their suitability to adequately address the impact type in question.

Three terms are worthy of mention concerning the terminology used in this paper: ‘*cross-border*’, ‘*impact*’ and ‘*risk*’. A highly diverse spectrum of terminologies are used to describe climate impacts transmitting across interdependent systems (Bednar-Friedl et al., 2022; Benzie et al., 2017; Simpson et al., 2021). In this paper, we adopt the terminology and definitions proposed by Carter et al. (2021, p. 2), where they describe cross-border climate change impacts as “consequences of climate change that occur remotely from the location of their initial impact, where both impacts, and potentially also responses to those impacts such as adaptation, are transmitted across one or more borders”. The closest equivalent to the term ‘cross-border impacts’ in the literature is ‘transboundary impacts’, though there are numerous nuanced variants applied to the same phenomenon (many summarised by Benzie et al., 2019).

While the terms risk and impact are sometimes used interchangeably, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) refers to potential impacts where those impacts are adverse (IPCC, 2019). While the IPCC acknowledges that there may also be beneficial impacts, framing impacts as risks in these terms limits the analysis of cross-border impacts by ignoring part of the full distribution of impacts of climate change that occur in reality. Therefore, to avoid ambiguity and in alignment with Carter et al., (2021), we use the neutral term ‘impact’ to refer to the effects triggered by climate and then propagated across borders. We do also refer to ‘risk’, but here the term is used to describe the aggregate potential impacts received by a given actor for which a response is required – the ‘recipient risk’ (Carter et al., 2021). Unlike the IPCC definition, risk here describes potential impacts that may be adverse, beneficial or neutral. Hence the framework is applicable to all kinds of impacts, though most examples we present focus on adverse impacts, as these are usually of greatest societal concern.

In the following sections, we first assemble the elements of the suggested framework and discuss the rationale of proposing a new response framework to cross-border climate impacts. Section 3 applies the framework in two case studies – one historical and one hypothetical, drawn from a policy simulation on the future of food security. Section 4 discusses the potential usefulness and limitations of the framework, with some conclusions drawn in Section 5.

2. A framework for responding to cross-border climate impacts

Traditional responses to climate change impacts have been criticised for defining climate risk as a local challenge confined to national borders (e.g., Benzie and Persson, 2019; Liverman, 2016). These approaches generally fail to capture system interdependencies and cross-border climate impacts (Paterson and Guida, 2022). Previous work has conceptualized the potential risks and rippling effects of neglecting such interdependencies (Carter et al., 2021; Challinor et al., 2018; Hedlund et al., 2018a; Moser and Hart, 2015) and recent studies (Harris et al., 2022; Schweizer, 2021) seek to take these interdependencies further into account through the development of frameworks based on concepts of risk governance and risk ownership. More broadly (and see Schweizer, 2021) is the need for a ‘multi-level and multi-actor’ framework for investigating the interdependencies of systemic risks and deciding on appropriate policy options.

This paper responds to that challenge. We propose a framework for facilitating the identification and selection of responses to cross-border climate impacts and recommend a comprehensive process for designing adaptation measures to address the associated risks and opportunities, suitable for different

scales and systems. The framework outlines a sequence of steps, through which response options and governance modalities for addressing cross-border climate impacts can be filtered and assessed for their appropriateness, considering potential negative or undesirable consequences. While building on many existing risk management frameworks, we add value by distinguishing the identification of actor constellations as an important and necessary step, and by circling back from responses to impacts, recognising that any type of response could potentially create or redistribute risks within the impact transmission system.

Figure 1. Response framework for cross-border climate impacts. The framework distinguishes between the impact transmission system (blue area) – the space where the initial impact(s) of a climate trigger occur and propagate across borders; the response transmission system (green area) – the space where responses to the propagated impacts are designed and implemented; and the external system (yellow area) – the space where key drivers that interact with the transmission of impacts and responses may be located. Different gradients of green shading within the impact transmission system indicate varying levels of strength and ability to respond to a given impact. The present-day context, where all systems operate, evolves into a number of alternative future contexts (illustrated as a stack of scenarios or storylines), indicating that the impact and transmission systems could potentially develop and follow alternative trajectories. The location of the borders in the diagram abstract, as cross-border impacts may cascade across single or multiple borders. (Carter et al., 2021).

The elements of the framework are illustrated in Figure 1. The framework consists of five building blocks:

1. Cross-border climate impact types
2. Actor constellations
3. Response types and governance modalities
4. Response appropriateness
5. Response effects and consequences

Step 1 of the framework is an impact identification and assessment. A typology of cross-border climate impacts based on three attributes (scale, dynamic, and level of complexity) is developed to guide the process of impact classification and characterisation. In steps 2 and 3, the framework introduces constellations of actors affected by and involved in responding to the impacts and a classification of response types. The sequence of these two elements within the framework depends on the case where the framework is being applied. For instance, if the framework is being used as a tool to identify and select an appropriate response(s) to an ongoing or anticipated impact, it would be important to first characterise constellations of actors affected by and potentially involved in responding to the impact before exploring different response types that could be appropriate given the nature of the impact and identified actors. In contrast, if the framework is utilized for evaluating historical cases of responding to cross-border climate impacts, it should be possible to identify response type(s) alongside a classification of the impacts, and then to characterise the constellation of actors who were involved in implementing the response(s).

Step 4 outlines a logical process for linking impact and response types and considering the level of appropriateness of alternative response types in addressing a given impact type. The concept of appropriateness here is analytical rather than normative, relating to the nature and characteristics of the impact, and applying actor constellations, levels of coordination, and governance capacity as criteria. Step 5 provides guidance in assessing the effectiveness of the response (in reducing and/or absorbing the risk(s) and enhancing opportunities) and revealing undesirable effects, acknowledging that any response to cross-border climate impacts could potentially create, redistribute, or exacerbate risks to other entities within the system.

In the following sections, we introduce the response framework step by step.

2.1. Framing cross-border climate impacts

A key challenge for climate change impact assessment and adaptation is to identify different types of impacts and how they cascade through interdependent networks (Adger et al., 2018). Different cross-border climate impacts exhibit different characteristics and transmission dynamics, and thus result in different types of risks and opportunities to societies. Actors addressing a cross-border climate impact and the response options available to them, therefore, significantly depend on the type of cross-border impact in question.

While classical approaches to risk classification categorize risks based on levels of probability and extent of damage (Horton et al., 2010), more recent approaches suggest that for risk appraisal and management in complex systems, there is a need to look beyond probability (Aven, 2016; Aven and Renn, 2015; Stirling, 2010) and incorporate additional dimensions such as complexity, uncertainty and ambiguity (Aven and Renn, 2015; Cox Jr, 2012). Systemic risk frameworks, such as the framework of Schweizer (2021), address this need by differentiating between simple and systemic risks, and attributing systemic risks with high complexity and uncertainty, transboundariness, non-linearity, and tipping points.

Focusing on the risks risen from climate impacts, Simpson et al. (2021) use four determinants – hazard, vulnerability, exposure and response – to classify extremely complex climate risks. Zscheischler et al. (2020) develop a typology of compound weather and climate events and distinguish between preconditioned, multivariate, temporally compounding and spatially compounding. In a case study on New Zealand, Lawrence et al., (2020) create an informal typology of climate events that may have

cascading impacts and differentiate between slowly emerging and ongoing, widening climate variability, extremes, and combined impacts.

A range of studies focusing on cross-border climate impacts utilise categories based on a set of impact areas or pathways through which impacts transmit across sectors and borders (Hildén et al., 2016; Moser and Hart, 2015; PwC, 2013). For example, Benzie and Carlsen (2016) and Hedlund et al. (2018) suggest four impact propagation pathways, including trade, finance, people and biophysical, and develop a national-level vulnerability index accordingly. Benzie et al. (2019) add psychological, infrastructure and geopolitical pathways to this framework. Assessing the propagation of climate impacts across sectors and borders, Challinor et al. (2018) develop a typology of risk transmission mechanisms, distinguishing between those that are climatically and resource generated. Carter et al. (2021) present a conceptual framework for understanding cross-border climate impacts. Using the scale and dynamic of impact transmission, they explore a set of indicative examples of cross-border climate impacts.

We adopt and combine three attributes from the conceptual framework for cross-border climate impacts (Carter et al., 2021) and the systemic risk framework (Schweizer, 2021) to structure our typology of cross-border climate impacts: impact transmission scale and impact transmission dynamic from Carter et al. (2021), and complexity from Schweizer (2021).

In the first layer of our typology, scale (also called transboundary type) and transmission dynamic types are used to identify a set of impact types (figure 2). Carter et al. (2021) describe impact transmission scales as different levels or tiers at which cross-border climate impacts may be propagated across borders. Transmission dynamic refers to the characteristics and configurations of impact propagation flow from the initial impact to the recipient risk. In the second layer, complexity is used as an additional attribute for a more intricate understanding of different types of cross-border climate impacts. According to Schweizer (2021), [high] complexity refers to the stochastic nature of systemic risks. We adopt complexity as a continuous attribute (low to high) and use it to cluster cross-border climate impact types into four categories (figure 3)².

² It is worthy of mention that Schweizer (2021) defines systemic risks as necessarily requiring a high level of transboundariness – having ripple effects spread out across system boundaries. While transboundariness in this framework is a serial attribute, as opposed to scale in the conceptual framework of Carter et al. (2021) which is a characteristicum, both concepts seem to be describing the transboundary and cascading nature of systemic risks.

Figure 2. Cross-border climate impact typology (first layer). The horizontal axis shows different types of transmission dynamic, including single tier, cascades, compound, and feedback. The vertical axis shows scale or transboundary types, including neighbouring, remote, and multi-regional.

Figure 3. Different levels of complexity within the cross-border climate impacts typology. The shading illustrates the level of complexity (light yellow=low, yellow=medium, orange=high). The lines between shadings are notional, as impact appraisal and matching specific impacts to alternative impacts clusters could be subjective.

The use of scale and dynamic as key variables provides an opportunity to account for important spatial dimensions and propagation modes in classifying cross-border climate impacts. Scale is an essential attribute for understanding constellations of actors, and the extent and magnitude of their operation and influence, and thus plays a critical role in identifying and designing effective responses (Mechler et al., 2019). Cross-border climate impacts cascade in many different configurations, interacting with multiple system components. Using transmission dynamic as an attribute offers a structured approach for understanding system components and identifying key interventions points for targeting responses. While the Carter et al. (2021) framework presents a logic for cross-border impact conceptualisation using scale and dynamic, it does not go further to combine the two attributes to clearly identify different ‘types’ of cross-border climate impacts.

Similarly, while being informative for identification of systemic risks in general, the Schweizer (2021) framework is neither specific to systemic *climate* risks, nor address potential opportunities caused by climate impacts, and thus lacks an acceptable level of compatibility in cross-border climate impact classification. In addition, it fails to provide a structure for exploring different configurations of risk transmission across systems. We therefore take an additional step of structuring a clear typology of cross-border climate impacts as the starting point of the response framework. The typology provides a clear classification of cross-border climate impacts and facilitates the differentiation of cross-border climate impacts from systemic climate risks – which are sometimes used interchangeably in the literature – demonstrating what types of cross-border climate impacts have certain characteristics to pose systemic climate risks to societies at large.

2.1.1. Cross-border climate impact typology

Using the three dimensions discussed above, we identify four clusters of cross-border climate impacts:

- *Simple cross-border climate impacts* occur in one location and transmit to adjacent geographical regions (neighbouring) or distant locations (remote) in a cascade from one system component to the other (single-tier). The cascade could be escalating, amplified in each system component compared to the previous one, or diminishing, reduced in each system component compared to the previous one. The spatial and dynamic complexity of these impacts is low (e.g., the impacts of flooding caused by the melting of glaciers upstream between two neighbouring countries that share a river basin).
- *Spatially complex cross-border climate impacts* occur in one location and propagate to the recipient location via system components located in more than one jurisdiction (multi-regional). The transmission dynamic of these impacts is a single-tier cascade. These impacts are characterised by low dynamic complexity and high spatial complexity (e.g., the impacts of decreased supply of coffee in the global south to import-dependent regions in the global north, through linear agricultural supply chains with relatively straightforward links between producers, processors, and consumers).
- *Dynamically complex cross-border climate impacts* transmit to neighbouring or remote regions. The transmission dynamic of these impacts could involve cascade tiers with associated risks and opportunities at multiple system components (cascades), caused in multiple different locations before converging to affect the recipient (compound), or originate amplifying feed back between multiple system components (feedback). These impacts are characterised by high dynamic complexity and low spatial complexity (e.g., the impacts in Europe – in the form of

migration – of a decline in food production in Sahel resulting from complex multi-dimensional dynamics between climate events such as drought, and non-climate events, such as conflict).

- *Systemic cross-border climate impacts* transmit to the recipient location via multiple system components across more than one jurisdiction (multi-regional). Their transmission dynamic could be multi-tier cascades (also called cascades in short), compound, or feedback. They are characterised by high spatial and dynamic complexity. (e.g., the impacts in Europe – in the form of food affordability crisis – of global food market's inflation which is caused by the simultaneous occurrence of a crop failure in Africa resulting from prolonged droughts, and a decline in food production in Ukraine resulting from war).

2.2. Framing risk recipients and risk owners

The identification of risk recipients and owners who are affected by and could take responsibility for addressing a cross-border climate impact is crucial to designing responses and understanding the appropriateness of different response types. Any governance process for assessing and addressing risks and opportunities risen from an impact inevitably starts with the notion of risk ownership and the nature and extent of recipients' agency to act.

There are different applications of the term 'risk owners': to those affected; to those who pay for risk management (Semieniuk et al., 2022); to those considered responsible and accountable for the management process (Juhola, 2019); and to all those parties who pay for, manage, and are accountable for risk management (explicitly or by default) (Young et al., 2015). We understand risk recipients as those who are affected by an impact, and risk respondents or owners as those who address and respond to an impact. While risk ownership is a choice, responsibility, or capacity to manage the risk, risk recipients are those who experience the risk in the first place, and usually the first actors to respond to it. Both recipients and owners could potentially be actors, taking responsibility and agency in addressing the impact.

The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report recognizes that multiple actors, besides governments, can deliver adaptation action including businesses and not-for-profit organizations. It particularly acknowledges empirical evidence indicating that the role of private actors (both for-profit and non-profit) and transnational networks in adaptation initiatives has grown more significant since the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report, some eight years previously (IPCC, 2022). Literature shows that governance processes and arrangements for addressing climate change impacts often engage all three actor groups (public, for-profit, and non-profit), or a combination of them (Bevir, 2011; Bulkeley et al., 2014; Schneider, 2012; Stoker, 1998).

In our framework, we use actor groups as the first attribute for classifying actor constellations, and adopt the grouping of actors suggested extensively in the literature, distinguishing between public and private sector actors. (Andonova et al., 2009; Bulkeley et al., 2014). However, within the private sector group, we recognise distinctions between business actors and civil society or non-governmental organizations in their characteristics, interests, motivations, and functions in adaptation governance processes. We refer to constellations of actors as combinations of risk recipients and risk owners from multiple actor groups.

Scale is another important attribute for identifying actors and their sphere of operation in addressing cross-border climate impacts. As impacts transmit across borders, it is important to differentiate between management processes at different scales. Accordingly, we adopt scale of operation as the second dimension for classifying actor constellations, distinguishing between national, transnational, and limited scale types. We added a third scale option – limited – to the two most dominant in the literature (Andonova et al., 2009; Bernstein and Cashore, 2012; Smit et al., 2000), since in some cases, it might be only a small number of jurisdictions that are involved in an impact transmission system, arguably making more complex forms of transnational governance redundant as a response.

2.2.1. Classifying actor constellations

Using actor group and scale of operation, we identify different constellations of actors that have a mandate or role in responding to cross-border climate impacts.

- *Public actor constellations* include states, national, regional, and local governments, public institutions, and other sub-units of governments at either national, limited, or transnational levels. International organizations, such as the United Nations and the World Bank, are considered as public actors (Andonova et al., 2009; Bulkeley et al., 2014) since they are formed by a group of states engaging in the context of global governance. Public actor constellations could be formed at national or jurisdictional scale (e.g., The Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative – RGGI), among a small number of system components (e.g., US-Australia partnership for climate governance), and at transnational scale (e.g., the International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives – ICLEI).
- *Private actor constellations* include non-state for-profit and/or non-profit entities. For-profit actors encompass the private sector (corporations, and companies), while non-profit actors consist of civil society and non-governmental organisations and grassroot and community groups. Constellations of private actors could emerge and develop at national and jurisdictional, limited, and transnational scales (e.g., World Business Council for Sustainable Development – WBCSD, World’s Youth for Climate Justice).
- *Constellations of actors at the recipient location* include a combination of public and private (both for-profit and non-profit) actors at national and jurisdictional level. Depending on the impact, these actor constellations can include national and local governments, national and local businesses, local communities, national non-governmental organisations and grassroot groups and networks. These constellations of actors can be seen in multi-level governance processes at national scale where different levels of government (e.g., national, federal, regional, local) and non-governmental actors collaborate for addressing a risk issue (Amundsen et al., 2010; Bauer and Steurer, 2014; Corfee-Morlot et al., 2009) (e.g., the landscape of climate adaptation policy in Canada – multi-level mosaic – where a range of governmental organizations at federal, territorial, provincial and municipal levels work together with non-governmental actors to plan and implement adaptation activities (Bauer and Steurer, 2014; Dickinson and Burton, 2011)).
- *Constellations of actors at limited system components* include national or jurisdictional actors inclusive of all actor groups (i.e., public, and private) at the recipient location and another key system component. This would occur when actors in a recipient location coordinate with a relatively inclusive set of actors addressing the same cross-border climate impact at a few other locations within the impact transmission system. An inclusive constellation of actors at limited

scale could encompass public, for-profit actors, and non-profit actors (e.g., constellation of key actors in Japan and Thailand responding in coordination to floods in 2011 that originated in Thailand but also generated risks to Japan (Promchote et al., 2016)).

- *Constellations of actors across the entire system* include public and private actor groups at transnational scale (i.e., all jurisdictions affected across the impact transmission system). These constellations of actors have the potential to be the most inclusive, bringing together national and sub-national governments, international organizations, for-profit actors operating across the transmission system, and national and transnational NGOs. There are several existing transnational constellations of actors working within climate mitigation governance (e.g., Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Partnership – REEEP, Forest Carbon Partnership Facility – FCPF). However, the strong focus towards mitigation action in the transnational realm (Bulkeley et al., 2014) makes it difficult to find examples of transnational constellations of actors focusing on adaptation, particularly in response to cross-border climate impacts.

2.3. Framing responses to cross-border climate impacts

The scientific literature reveals a few studies that aim to explore different strategies and approaches for responding to cascading risks. In a case study on the UK, Pescaroli (2018) develops an integrative process for understanding the perception and management of cascading disasters and applying that knowledge base in designing preparedness strategies. The paper recommends options to better address cascading climate risks such as multi-agency coordination and organisational resilience. Miller and Pescaroli (2018) discuss the importance of psychosocial and cultural approaches and modalities for risk recipients and owners in response to cascading disasters. Lawrence et al. (2020) suggest that institutional arrangements, community engagement, funding and political leadership are all paramount for addressing cascading climate impacts. However, most explorations of responses to cross-border climate impacts have thematic focuses which limit their applicability to other cases. Attempts to design generic and comprehensive classifications of response types for addressing cross-border climate impacts remains limited.

To take a first step towards addressing this gap, we develop a generic typology of responses to cross-border climate impacts. We define a response as a proactive or reactive intervention to address a cross-border climate impact through tackling, managing, or diverting from the risks and/or enhancing, or exploiting the opportunities resulting from that impact. To develop the typology, We use response transmission targets and dynamics as the key attributes, where the former indicates the intervention point to which responses are targeted, and the latter refers to the response propagation sequence (Carter et al., 2021). The conceptual framework of Carter et al. (2021) presents a set of indicative examples for response transmission targets and dynamics. In our response typology, we use those examples as a starting point and expand on target options and dynamic configurations to characterise a set of plausible response types (figure 4). Similar to the impact typology, we recognize that the coverage of response typology might be incomplete, and further research is needed for expansion.

2.3.1. Response typology

Figure 4. Cross-border climate impact response typology

- *Block* refers to responses focused on preventing the propagating impacts from affecting the recipient through setting up barriers at one or more points between the initial impact and its transmission towards the recipient location. The response dynamic aims to block the cascade of impacts before it arrives at the recipient location and affects the people or assets at risk.
- *Domestic adaptation* refers to responses at the location of the recipient, either to reduce the vulnerability of people or assets or to increase adaptive capacity and resilience through adaptation action. This response dynamic aims to absorb the impact as opposed to blocking it.
- *Adaptation at origin* refers to responses directed at the source of an impact, i.e., where impact(s) originally occurred. This response dynamic aims to mitigate, manage, redirect, or adapt to impact(s) at the initial location.
- *Adaptation within the transmission system* describes interventions at the location of a key system component. The response target is an optimal node for intervention, a system component in which the recipient has influence, interest, or authority to intervene. The response dynamic could range from breaking the cascade by blocking the impact from affecting the targeted system component, or facilitating mitigation of, or adaptation to, the impact at the node.
- *Adaptation via a third party* refers to cases where the recipient targets a third party (an entity outside the impact transmission system or an external system component) to intervene and influence the impact transmission system. Interventions could be made at the initial source of the impact or at one or more system components within the third party's sphere of influence.
- *Substitution* is also directed at a third party, not involved in, or affected by the impact transmission system. The response dynamic aims to substitute the source of the impact by

opening alternative channels and reducing the dependency of the system and vulnerability to the cascading impact.

- *System-wide adaptation* describes cases where the recipient targets interventions at the entire impact transmission system aiming at building system-wide resilience. The magnitude and scale of interventions at different system components are variable and depend on the scale and sphere of influence that the recipient has at each link or node. Responses may be phased and staggered in time to target optimal intervention nodes and “critical points of vulnerability over less crucial elements” (Carter et al., 2021).
- *Pseudo-responses* refer to cases where the recipient implements measures that do not address actual impacts, or where impacts are used rhetorically as justification for taking actions that do not constructively or genuinely aim to address the impact or society’s vulnerability to that impact. Response dynamics could be variable; the actual aim of such responses is to achieve objectives or protect interests other than those primarily affected by the cross-border climate impact (e.g., cases where the recipient aims to deflect attention from the risks caused by the initial cross-border impact or seeks to gain advantage from it in some way).

Response types are then clustered (based on their similarities in targets and dynamics, and accounting for the different constellations of actors who can implement them within their sphere of influence) with five groups of governance modalities emerging. Each of these groups – internal adaptation, targeted collaboration, external collaboration, broad collaboration, and deflection – indicates an alternative approach to the governance of cross-border climate impacts.

2.3.2. Governance modalities for addressing cross-border climate impacts

The concept of governance – the complex processes and interactions that constitute patterns of rule – recognises that a range of actor groups, formal and informal, can exercise authority, power of influence and decision making through diverse modalities (Bevir, 2011; Bulkeley et al., 2014; Renn, 2017; Schweizer and Renn, 2019). Forms of governance range from formal regulation, deliberation, agenda setting and negotiation, to knowledge sharing and capacity building. Governance processes involve a plurality of stakeholders (public and private) linked together in networks that often span sectoral and jurisdictional boundaries, meaning that power dynamics and dependencies formed in the relationships between actors must be recognized and accounted for (Bevir, 2011; Bulkeley et al., 2014; Schneider, 2012; Stoker, 1998).

Different modes of governance have been identified in political sciences, public policy, and risk research based on different attributes, such as the degree to which processes are top-down or bottom-up, the relationships between state and non-state actors, and levels of inclusion and engagement (Greve and Hodge, 2010; Klinke and Renn, 2021; Renn, 2017; Treib et al., 2007). Similarly, approaches to climate change governance have been analysed and classified based on the actors involved – public, private or both – and the primary functions of climate governance spaces – information sharing, capacity building and implementation, or rule setting (Andonova et al., 2009; Bauer and Steurer, 2014). Direction of authority, sources of institutional legitimacy, initiating and implementing actor groups, and dominant policy instruments are extensively used for exploring governance approaches and pathways to climate change adaptation (Bednar and Henstra, 2018; Dzebo and Adams, 2023).

As literature on climate change adaptation emphasizes the importance of collaboration in governing climate impacts and associated risks (Bednar and Henstra, 2018; Biagini et al., 2014; Börzel, 2011;

Bulkeley et al., 2014; Dzebo, 2019; Leck and Simon, 2013; Marie-Valentine and Thomas, 2018; Renn, 2017; Talebian et al., 2021; Treib et al., 2007), we used the scale and nature of collaboration within actor constellations as the second key criterion (alongside groups of response types as the first) in the framing of alternative governance modalities to address cross-border climate impacts. Accordingly, each governance modality signals a different level and dynamic of coordination and collaboration between actors (shown in table 1).

	Internal adaptation	Targeted collaboration	External collaboration	Broad collaboration	Deflection
Response types	 Pseudo-response				
Actor constellations	Public and private actors at national scale	Public and private actors at limited locations	Public and private actors at limited locations	Public and private actors at transnational scale	Public and private actors
Capacity for influence	Internal influence; Targets risk recipient	Limited sphere of influence; Targets one component within the impact transmission system	Limited sphere of influence; Targets an entity outside the impact transmission system	Broad sphere of influence and motivation for coordination; Targets the entire impact transmission system	Limited sphere of influence and no motivation for collaboration; Targets outside of the system boundaries

Table 1. Five governance modalities for addressing cross-border climate impacts³

2.4. Response appropriateness: Linking impact and response types

Linking impact types and response types is an essential step towards providing actionable recommendations for addressing cross-border climate impacts. To our knowledge, there are no generic impact-response typologies in the field of cross-border climate impacts. Studies focusing on specific fields like trade, supply chain management and agriculture investigate different cross-border climate impacts that might impose risks to a certain sector and/or social context and try to develop specific responses to address those risks (Becker et al., 2013; Bednar-Friedl et al., 2022; Smit and Skinner, 2002). But they are often specific to their thematic area and lack a broad enough conceptualization to be relevant to other fields or reframed into a generic impact-response typology.

³ Our objective in this paper is to develop a conceptual framework for responding to cross-border climate impacts; we thus stop at presenting a set of generic governance modalities and do not attempt to drill down into institutional specifics and divisions of responsibility, which are context specific and subject to the power relations involved in each case. The question of ‘who does what’ or ‘who should do what’ should be answered through the application of the response framework to different contexts and case studies.

To address this gap, we construct a logical process for pairing impact types with response types through three criteria: actor constellation, cross-scale coordination, and governance capacity. The process starts with an exploration of actor constellations, since the type of response that is feasible and appropriate for addressing a given cross-border climate impact depends heavily on the type of actor groups (including risk recipients and risk owners). The scale of operation of actor groups within the constellation is also important for assessing the extent to which responses based on cross-scale cooperation (across the impact transmission system) are feasible, or if they will be limited to the location of the recipient.

The second criterion for linking impact and response types is the level of coordination across scales. Studies on inclusive policymaking provide extensive evidence of how the level and efficacy of coordination affects cross-scale and cross-sectoral policy processes (Jochim and May, 2010; Lodge and Wegrich, 2014; Peters, 2015). Motives and incentives to coordinate (including political interests), and structures that provide enabling or constraining environments, may vary depending on the different parties involved and will affect, to a high degree, what responses best suit particular impacts. Moreover, addressing different impact types implies various levels of cross-scale coordination and accordingly necessitate the selection of different response types. A simple cross-border climate impact originated in a neighbouring location, for instance, could potentially be addressed with limited coordination capacity and through existing cooperation mechanisms, while a spatially complex impact, is arguably better tackled through multiple interventions within the transmission system, and hence, require higher levels of coordination across scales.

Finally, we selected governance capacity as the third criterion for exploring the appropriateness of response types to given impact types. The concept of governance capacity – which has sometimes been used interchangeably with administrative capacity and policy capacity – refers to a broad and comprehensive system of resources for supporting policymaking (Howlett and Ramesh, 2014; Howlett and Saguin, 2018, 2018; Lodge and Wegrich, 2014). According to Bulkeley et al. (2014), three aspects of governance capacity are important for assessing the management of climate change impacts and associated risks, especially in transnational and multi-scale contexts: level of coordination, implementation, and administrative capacity (resources and staff deployed). We consider cross-scale coordination as a separate attribute (for reasons outlined above). However, we consider coordination between actor groups (public and private at each scale) as a dimension of governance capacity alongside implementation and administrative capacity.

Figure 5. Logical process for exploring response appropriateness

Figure 5 shows a simplified visualisation of the logical process, illustrating the three criteria and the questions formulated to measure them, to assess the appropriateness of a given response type and a governance modality for addressing a given impact type. Anticipating and monitoring response effects (including potential unwanted consequences) then provides an opportunity for researchers and other actors to adjust and re-evaluate responses or select and combine additional response types and modalities for a more comprehensive strategy to manage cross-border climate impacts.

We recognize that in the absence of sufficient data to analyse and deduce response appropriateness for cross-border climate impacts, there is a danger of resorting to the use of normative statements and value-based judgments, which fall neither within the objective nor scope of this paper. However, in establishing a set of criteria and designing an abstract but logical process for assessing response appropriateness, we offer some observations and propositions on pairing impact and response types, accounting for actor constellations, cross-scale coordination, and governance capacity.

Smaller scale actor constellations have limited spheres of influence and operation, and thus limited capacity to affect the impact transmission system. Actor constellations marked by higher levels of inclusivity and coordination across scales facilitate or even warrant collaborative governance modalities and response types focused on the impact transmission system in part or whole. In other words, for system-wide resilience (and broad collaboration as a governance modality) to be appropriate for addressing a cross-border climate impact, harnessing, or establishing a transnational constellation of actors within the system, and mechanisms for coordination between those actors, is necessary.

When applying the proposed impact-response pairing process for identifying future responses, a dynamic loop between the assessment of coordination level and governance capacity can be imagined. Lower levels of coordination can be compensated by enhancing governance capacity within the system and at different scales of operation. Similarly, lower implementation and administrative governance capacity can be substituted by improving coordination, facilitating collective action, and fostering synergies.

Finally, for every impact type, there could be more than one feasible and appropriate response type for adapting to the associated risks. This has been observed in historical cases of cross-border climate impacts, where different recipients address the same impact with different approaches (See appendix A). The selection of response types largely depends on the set criteria, and other influential factors including political interests and power relations at national and transnational scales, levels of motivation for coordination and collaboration, and consistency and coherence with other policy objectives and measures.

For example, a systemic cross-border climate impact like spikes in global food prices could be best addressed through broad collaboration between actors and a combination of short-term responses (e.g., substitution and diversification) and long-term measures (e.g., improving supply chain resilience and reforming food systems) at local, national, and transnational levels. At the same time, a risk recipient (e.g., a jurisdiction) that is politically isolated weak coordination links with the international community is less able to build a bilateral or transnational constellation of through a collaborative governance approach. However, it might have fairly sophisticated administrative and implementation capacity to govern the impact of a global food price spike within its national borders, and as such may respond through domestic interventions only, such as blocking the impact by reducing market dependency and increasing local crop production.

Deploying the set appropriateness criteria, the most effective governance approaches for addressing cross-border climate impacts involve combinations of response types and governance modalities, each of which are more appropriate for addressing certain types of risks and opportunities and targeting different time horizons. Looking at the response typology, it is clear that some response types are more reactive (e.g., block) and focused on immediate management of potential risks, while others may be more proactive and focused on ‘no regret’ options (e.g., system-wide adaptation). In assessing all response options – but particularly in assessing the efficacy of a governance approach based on a combination of response types – it will be important to account for policy coherence to avoid contradictions and foster synergies in policy outcomes and processes.

2.5. Response effects and implications

Responses to cross-border climate impact may have desirable as well as undesirable consequences and their effects may impact components of the response transmission system (e.g., different places, or social groups) in a variety of positive and negative ways. The conceptual framework should avoid naively assuming that all responses are positively motivated, or likely to result in positive outcomes for all. Indeed, the nature of complex systems is such that local responses often *drive* risk at the system level. These dynamics must therefore be recognised.

In an optimal case, responses would intentionally and successfully reduce risks associated with the impact, contributing enhanced resilience for all system components (i.e., system-wide resilience), not merely for the risk recipient in a narrow sense. “Successful” responses may also include those that capitalise on opportunities presented by cross-border climate impacts, where these occur.

Yet in many cases, responses enacted by risk recipients may exacerbate or redistribute risk. A response may be effective at one scale (e.g., for the risk recipient), whilst increasing risk elsewhere in the impact transmission system. For example, when a country responds to price shocks on international commodity markets by banning exports, it might successfully insulate domestic markets, while simultaneously exacerbating the magnitude of the shock for consumers in other countries, thus undermining resilience at the system level. Such response-effects may be intentional or unintentional. When recipients operate with bounded political remit, geographic scope or limited cognitive understanding of system complexities and dynamics, such unintended consequences become more likely.

In some cases, response effects may be intentionally designed to undermine resilience elsewhere in the system, where risk recipients see a geopolitical or strategic advantage from competitive action (e.g., based on a zero-sum framing of international cooperation). In other cases, domestic power asymmetries may result in powerful actors pursuing responses to cross-border climate impacts that advantage some social groups over others, possibly even undermining the resilience of marginalised groups or actors, whilst protecting or delivering benefits to the powerful. We have also noted above the potential for “pseudo responses”, where the risks resulting from cross-border climate impacts are used to motivate or frame responses that do not genuinely address the risk themselves but serve some other (e.g., political, or economic) objective.

These examples highlight the importance of clearly identifying and specifying “system boundaries” or “system definitions” in the process of assessing responses to cross-border climate impacts. When system boundaries are set or articulated broadly, marginal, distant, or under-represented system components can be explicitly identified, which may increase the likelihood that potential negative

response-effects will be described. When system boundaries are set narrowly, these response-effects are less likely to be rendered visible.

Given the high propensity for feedbacks and dynamic effects in complex cross-border systems, it therefore seems important to set broad rather than narrow system boundaries for the assessment of cross-border climate impacts and responses.

3. Operationalising the framework

To demonstrate the usefulness of the response framework, we present two case studies that articulate how the framework can assist in identifying and filtering responses to observed and prospective cross-border climate impacts.

In the first case study, we present a historical example, the food affordability crisis in the United Kingdom (UK). In 2010, the cross-border impacts of teleconnected crop failure in Pakistan and Russia caused a spike in global wheat prices, affecting food affordability in the UK (*systemic climate impact*). As the risk recipient, the UK responded by sending emergency funding to Pakistan (*adaptation at origin*) and expanding emergency food banks (*domestic adaptation*).

The objective of this case study is to demonstrate the usefulness of the framework in assessing observed responses to cross-border climate impacts. We use the existing literature to describe the impact type, actor constellations, response types and governance modalities used for addressing the impact. A conceptual diagram and description of this case study can be found in Appendix A.

The second case study describes a policy simulation of a hypothetical food crisis in 2026-2028. In 2026-2028, a rice blast epidemic in India and Bangladesh and severe droughts in North Africa and the Sahel lead to declines in food production, higher global prices for pesticides and fertilizer, extreme inflation in the global food market and climate-induced migration (*systemic climate impact*). The European Union (EU) and its Member States address the crisis through a number of responses such as border control to reduce migration (*block*), systematically encouraging agro-ecological solutions and regenerative agriculture (*system-wide adaptation*), sending adaptation funds to North Africa and the Sahel (*adaptation at origin*), and the provision of funding subsidies and consumer relief at the EU level (*domestic adaptation*).

The objective of this case study is to demonstrate the usefulness of the framework in identifying and designing responses to future cross-border climate impacts. The responses detailed were developed by a range of stakeholders who participated in simulation runs, adopting fictional roles. A conceptual diagram and description of this case study can be found in Appendix B.

4. Discussion

The boundaries of impact and response transmission systems, and conception of components within such systems, are subjective and depend on potential users of the framework. What might be understood as an external component, could be also categorized as a component within the impact or response transmission system from a different perspective. Moreover, the boundaries of the response transmission system are not static and can dynamically change over time and by implementation of every new response. For example, when an actor constellation influences an external system component through a 'substitution' response type, the response transmission system could potentially expand to include the new component and its links and connections to other influential components. In this sense, the definition of an impact or response transmission system is arbitrary, making the careful delineation

of system boundaries – before impact and responses are paired – a critical step in the process. This is particularly the case, given that the application of system boundaries very much influences the user's conception of governance modalities. A governance modality that is understood to be based on broad collaboration, might in fact be quite narrow, because the system boundaries are drawn around a small sub-system and fail to account for components in a wider system.

It is also important to note that the perception of risk, and of appropriateness of response, will be different from various vantage points. This framework has attempted to propose a series of logical criteria for assessing response 'appropriateness' – the nature and dynamic of the impact, the constellation of actors involved in responding to the impact, and the level of coordination and governance capacity at different scales – as opposed to deploying normative or value-based reasoning. But there are still subjective assessments involved in evaluating such criteria, and so the pairing of impact and response types could look very different when performed by different stakeholders or users of the framework – each with their own perspectives and interests.

The framework suggested here focuses on adaptation responses to cross-border climate impacts. However, we recognize that climate change mitigation is an essential response to alleviate impacts at all levels as it addresses the fundamental cause of anthropogenic climate changes. When an impact is highly uncertain and systemic, and collaboration in a complex system with multiple actors at multiple scales is not feasible, climate change mitigation may be the only appropriate response type. For instance, in the face of high impact low probability risks such as cascading tipping events, where local adaptive capacities are insufficient (Wunderling et al., 2022) and the abrupt nature of the impacts make effective collaboration on adaptation across scales challenging, climate change mitigation is a vital proactive response.

4.1. Enhancing knowledge

The response framework provides a structured process to understand and link different cross-border climate impacts and appropriate responses to address them. In combining typologies of impacts and responses, and characterising actor constellations and governance modalities, the framework integrates the processes of impact appraisal and response planning, and thus presents a comprehensive architecture for informing adaptation governance. Focusing on interactions between impacts and responses, and the propagation of both across jurisdictions, the framework enhances the understanding of opportunities and challenges for global collaboration on adaptation. In proposing a set of criteria for assessing response appropriateness, it supports the identification of impacts that require the strengthening of system-wide resilience, and the advantages of combining multiple response types, to structure inclusive governance modalities that (arguably) are rarely implemented in current adaptation efforts.

With climate change adaptation traditionally implemented at local level, understanding of cross-border climate impacts is nascent and the knowledge informing adaptation planning and practice is fragmented (Dellmuth and Gustafsson, 2021; Neil Adger et al., 2005; Persson, 2019). The response framework can potentially be used to systematically compare and integrate knowledge on cross-border climate impacts and responses across a diversity of scales and disciplines. The framework could also inform the design of future case studies on cascading climate impacts and response options, advancing the evidence base still further.

4.2. Informing policy

While adaptation is recognized as a global challenge in the international political process (United Nations, 2015), and an increasing number of national risk assessments draw attention to cross-border climate impacts, few adaptation plans propose concrete responses to address them or identify actors who could govern them (Harris et al., 2022). Adaptation policies are owned and steered at the national and jurisdictional level, in relative siloes, and frameworks for global adaptation governance are lacking. The response framework therefore helps address an important gap in adaptation policy, to identify and assess appropriate responses to such impacts.

Using the response framework, adaptation policymakers can identify cross-border climate impacts and map their propagation, accounting for their exposure and vulnerability to climate triggers beyond their usual jurisdictions. Having a comprehensive understanding of their vulnerability to local and cross-border climate risks, they can also identify the most appropriate adaptation responses – potentially addressing a wider range of risks and opportunities arising within and outside their scale of operation more effectively. The framework also assists policymakers to identify suitable intervention points for different response types and anticipate when broad or targeted collaboration with actors across scales and jurisdictions is necessary, when relying on internal adaptation and domestic capacity would bring the desired results, and when combining different modalities is called for to accommodate short-term adaptation and long-term resilience-building.

4.3. Limitations of the response framework

The response framework is research-oriented, abstract, and descriptive. It is a first attempt at developing typologies of cross-border climate impacts and responses and exploring the question of response appropriateness. While we set a number of criteria for assessing response appropriateness, one could imagine additional influential factors, especially with regard to different contexts. Although the framework at this stage could potentially inform policy in the ways mentioned above, it is designed as an analytical tool rather than a practical decision-support apparatus. Future application and testing of the framework in case studies could improve the framework's structure, and coverage of impact and response types.

The framework is primarily focused on spatial scale and geographical borders. While we acknowledge that a sectoral dimension is missing from the framework (i.e., the transmission of an impact across sectors, domains, and entities), we argue that bringing in sectoral types as an additional dimension adds new (and unnecessary) complexities. We address the issue of cross-sectoral cascades in the response framework's logic through delineating multiple system components.

4.4. Future research

We recognize a certain level of simplification in the structure of the response framework, specifically in describing actor constellations. While we recognize the importance of exploring governance spaces at an institutional level, we believe a generic response framework as proposed in this paper is a necessary first step to conceptualize different types of actor groups at different scales that could potentially be involved in addressing cross-border climate impacts. Moreover, we believe that institutional nuances in any given governance space are highly context specific.

At present, our understanding remains incomplete concerning how specific institutional characteristics influence the governance of cross-border climate impacts, and how the politics and power imbalances of their relationships affect the operationalisation and implementation of responses. Therefore, we believe that further work is required to capture and integrate the complexity of power relations at institutional level in this framework and to provide consistent empirical evidence of how such factors manifest under different governance approaches. A more nuanced understanding of the institutional division of labour, and the opportunities, obstacles, and drivers of cross-border climate impacts governance, is still to be achieved.

The inherent complexity of cross-border climate impacts, and the diversity of potential actors involved in addressing them, make it hard to identify who the risk owners are within and across scales and the relationships and power dynamics between them (Harris et al., 2022). Building on the abstract conceptualisation of actor constellations within the response framework, future research could seek to better account for risk ownership, as an analytical tool to identify roles, responsibilities sources of authority and legitimacy, and division of labour between state and non-state actor groups at an institutional level.

We recognize that climate change impacts could pose risks and opportunities, and actors could be at the receiving end of opportunities as well as risks. As such, adaptation to our understanding is about mitigating risks and enhancing opportunities. However, most examples and cases in this paper are focused on climate risks. While the response framework as a conceptual structure is applicable to identifying responses to climate change opportunities, future work and application of the framework is needed improve the coverage of response types more specifically appropriate for enhancing opportunities.

5. Conclusion

Climate change adaptation is a global challenge which requires cross-scale collaboration and transboundary governance. Studies on cross-border climate impacts demonstrate their potential to generate risks to different sectors, economies, societies, and ecosystems across the world, even those that were previously conceived to be less vulnerable to climate change. Yet, effective responses and governance modalities for addressing these impacts have received limited attention. A conceptual framework for articulating appropriate types of responses to cross-border climate impacts is a first step to addressing this gap and strengthening future adaptation planning at a transnational scale. The response framework presented in this paper offers a comprehensive architecture to identify and filter responses to cross-border climate impacts and formulate inquiries into their suitability and appropriateness. By remaining abstract and generic, the framework provides a structure that can be adopted to analyse adaptation actions over different jurisdictions and systems. The application of the response framework enhances understanding of the full suite of approaches and modalities to respond to cross-border climate impacts, as well as identifying potentially novel solutions, not only to adapt to cross-border climate impacts at smaller scales, but to also improve system-wide resilience and international collaboration cooperation on adaptation.

Appendices

Appendix A: Historical case study: food affordability crisis in the UK

Figure A.1 presents a conceptual diagram of Observed cross-border implications of teleconnected crop failures in Russia and Pakistan for affordability of food in the UK (based on Carter et al., 2020; and Challinor et al., 2018).

Figure A.1. Cross-border climate impacts and responses; case of food affordability crisis in the UK in 2010

In 2010, Arctic warming and its impacts on atmospheric Rossby waves (Mann et al., 2017) triggered an extreme heatwave in Russia (*climate trigger*) – which also affected large parts of Europe – and simultaneously, caused extreme rainfall and flooding (*climate trigger*) and consequently record flooding in Pakistan. These synchronous climate events caused massive crop declines in both countries (*initial impacts in two regions*) and affected global food security at large. The shortfall in global cereal production (*system component*) caused significant price increases in the global commodity markets (*system component*) (Challinor et al., 2018).

The initial impact cascaded across multiple national borders, disrupting global food markets, and creating exceptional food affordability crisis in many countries (*multi-regional in scale*). The impact transmission dynamic was compound where the initial impacts occurred in two different locations and then converged to affect the global market and countries depending on it. Going back to the impact typology as the first element of the framework, the described impact can be recognized as a systemic cross-border climate impact having a single underlying climate trigger leading to remote initial impacts propagating non-linearly through multiple regions due to dynamic complexities of climate and non-climate interactions and responses.

Countries (*risk recipients*) affected by price spikes in the global markets and associated risks (e.g., decreased food affordability in Bangladesh, Kenya, Indonesia, and Zambia (Hossain and Green, 2011), food-related civil unrest in Pakistan in 2010 (Natalini et al., 2019), etc.) reacted with different and largely inconsistent responses. For example, the Russian government introduced export bans to ensure internal food security for national populations, which in turn pushed up prices still further and worsened the global affordability crisis (Welton, 2011). While the export ban was a response from the Russian government's perspective (block), it was a system component amplifying the impact for other countries affected by the crisis (*response effect: exacerbate risk within the impact transmission system*).

As mentioned above, we focus here on the UK as the risk recipient and explore different response types and governance approaches used by UK actors to address the impact. The general populations, and specifically lower-income communities, were directly affected by increased UK food prices (*risk recipients*). Grassroots and non-profit private organizations, with the support from for-profit private entities (e.g., the trussell trust supported by food sector companies) were first to take ownership and respond to the crisis through upscaling and coordinating the operation of food banks across the country by 50% (Challinor et al., 2018). This response was initiated by non-profit and for-profit actors (*private actor constellation*) at the recipient location and focused on averting the risk and increasing national resilience (*domestic adaptation*).

The UK government also sought to address the food inflation and affordability crisis through emergency funding to assist flood management and recovery in Pakistan (Carter et al., 2021). This intervention was coordinated by public actors in the UK and Pakistan (*public actor constellation*) at bilateral scale and focused on managing the risk issue at the initial impact's location (*adaptation at origin*).

Considering the UK as the risk recipient, the constellation of actors consisted of public and private actors collaborating at national and bilateral levels. By engaging actors from within the transmission system (i.e., Pakistan), and combining alternative response types, key actors in the recipient location utilized an integrated governance modality and addressed the risk by internal adaptation, and targeted collaboration within the system. The appropriateness of response combinations and governance modality in this case could be explored through an investigation of coordination and governance capacity of the UK, and the possibility of engaging other system components and actors (e.g., public, and private actors in Russia, other countries affected by global market spikes, etc.).

Appendix B: Hypothetical future case study: food security crisis in the EU

A policy simulation is an experiential process where a group of participants, also called players, collectively explore a complex hypothetical scenario that resembles the real world and decide on policy interventions to address challenges within it (Duke and Geurts, 2004). Policy Simulations link qualitative and quantitative methods to support the exploration of future pathways and foster social learning (Mochizuki et al., 2021). They are similar to multi-player serious games insofar as they use

many game-like mechanics (Geurts et al., 2007), but they also resemble interactive theatre as they are open-ended and require participants to roleplay, creating opportunities for transformative learning (Crookall, 2010; Mezirow, 2000).

This policy simulation presents a hypothetical but plausible scenario of a global food crisis happening in 2026-2028. This crisis is initiated by a series of separate climate triggers causing initial impacts outside Europe, which then cascade across multiple regions and affect the EU and its member states. The topic choice reflected several prevailing crises (e.g., the war in Ukraine) and the reliance of the EU on the import of food products from other regions. This focus was motivated by the topic's connection with European food policies (e.g., Farm to Fork) and the possibility to explore the EU's social and political resilience to disruptions in trade and supply chains. The simulation uses this plausible scenario to illustrate how cross-border climate impacts can cascade into the EU, and to facilitate the co-production of possible policy responses by stakeholders. An earlier version of the response framework informed the design of the policy simulation and structured the stakeholder involvement, knowledge co-production, and debriefing during the simulation runs (Adameczak and Jarzabek, 2022).

Figure B.1 presents a conceptual diagram of the policy simulation storyline and selected policy ideas developed in the context of and during the simulation session. In the following, we break down how the response framework manifested in the simulation design and workshop debriefing, as well as running the simulation storyline through the framework to identify impact types, explore actor constellations, and characterise response types and suitability. Below, we present only a select part of the simulation storyline, and four of the twenty-one policy ideas developed by stakeholders. The full simulation diagram and the full list of policy recommendations are available as appendices (see supplementary materials 1 and 2).

Figure B.1. Conceptual diagram of the cross-border climate impacts and policy ideas developed participants responses; case of food security crisis in EU in 2026-2028

In 2026, a rice blast epidemic in India and Bangladesh (*initial impact*), is triggered by increasing warmth and humidity (*climate trigger*), resulting in dramatic crop losses and a surge in the demand for pesticides (Asibi et al., 2019). Simultaneously, a severe drought in North Africa and Sahel (*initial impact*) is triggered by a prolonged lack of precipitation (*climate trigger*), which leads to declines in food production and worsen the ongoing local and regional conflicts, such as the clash between Morocco and

the Western Sahara Independence Movement (Dworkin, 2022). In turn, the exacerbated conflict leads to disruptions in phosphates production and trade, since Morocco is a key global supplier of phosphates used for fertilizer production (Tanchum, 2022). The surge in short-term demand for agrochemicals in India and the phosphates disruption in Morocco jointly cause spectacular increases in agrochemicals prices worldwide. Farmers in the EU struggle to cope with resulting increases in production costs and simultaneous lower crop yields due to successive droughts, together resulting in lower crop yields and the prospect of. As a result, many of them financial losses and liquidity problems (elevated risk due to *systemic cross-border climate impacts*).

The introduction of regulation in line with the EU's Farm to Fork strategy aiming to a 20% reduction in the use of agrochemicals (European Commission, 2022) is perceived as an agrochemicals ban by a majority of EU farmers, who blame the European policies as partially responsible for decreased crop yields. This only amplifies farmers' lack of trust towards the EU's agricultural policies and triggers widespread protests in several member states. Food producers' financial losses, coupled with other crises in the storyline, engenders high food prices in the EU. European households must deal with dramatic increases in the costs of living. Food producing companies struggle with the higher production costs and decreasing demand for non-essential goods. As a result, many businesses in the agriculture, food and beverage sectors are at risk of defaulting (*systemic cross-border climate impact*). The inability of the EU businesses to pay their debts spells trouble for the EU banks, due to unpaid loans which feedback to amplify farmers' and food producers' liquidity problems, as credit is now more difficult to obtain (*systemic cross-border climate impact*). Taken together, the different financial impacts, further destabilise the whole EU economy.

The destabilisation of EU economy (caused by record high food prices, defaulting businesses, job losses and other related issues) combined with a lack of trust and widespread backlash against EU policies, result in a rise of radical political movements across the EU who attempt to capitalize on the unfolding food and economic crisis (*systemic cross-border climate impact*). The possibility of increased migration from North Africa to Europe due to climate-related conflicts and increased cross-border mobility (*systemic cross-border climate impact*) also feeds back into the rise of radical politics in Europe.

Within this stylised simulated context, participants took on the roles of select EU recipient countries and other actors, such as EU Directorate-General representatives, non-EU countries from Europe and North Africa, think tanks, non-governmental organizations, and business organizations. This arrangement aimed at simulating real-life inclusive actor constellations across scales and guiding the participants through the negotiation processes required to agree on policy interventions that could gather widespread support. Within the simulation, participants received instructions from their department directors, alerting them to the interests of the countries and organizations they represented. In addition, they were also exposed to the influence of various lobbyists representing the interests of key actors excluded from the simulation (e.g., via fictional emails received on the mobile app used for the policy simulation).

The main task for participants was to design and propose responses to the cross-border climate impacts presented in the simulation. At the beginning of the simulation session, participants received initial, pre-defined policy propositions from various groups. The design of these policies was guided by the response framework and represented different types of responses, and governance modalities. When the participants designed their own policies, they were, to some extent, using initial policies as examples, hence building on some of the concepts in the response framework. Table B.1 presents four selected policies developed by simulation participants and matches them with the response typology and

governance modalities developed here. These policies are also presented in the conceptual diagram (Figure B.1).

Policy idea (response)	Short description (for full description of policy ideas see supplementary material C)	Response type	Governance modality
Stronger EU border control	Stronger EU border control to regulate and manage migration.	Block	Internal adaptation
Focus funds on agricultural, farming, and consumer relief	Urging EU governments to allocate funds practically to local agricultural sector and farming, and to consumer relief from the food crisis.	Domestic adaptation	Internal adaptation
Africa-EU food systems partnership	Designating 15% of EU's 2027-2033 research and innovation budget to projects on adaptation and food systems support in Africa and 5% on EU-Africa food systems collaboration and knowledge transfer.	Adaptation at origin	Targeted collaboration within the system
Implement precision farming	Implementing precision farming [in the EU] for more controlled agrochemicals usage and decreasing the dependence on outside-EU agrochemicals imports.	Adaptation within the transmission system	Targeted collaboration within the system
Invest in the MENA's urban resilience to reduce the need for migration	Urging the EU to increase its ODA spending to the targeted 0.7% GNI and focus it on the investments in MENA rural and agricultural resilience, cities' infrastructure, jobs, and services to support the MENA countries' in managing the challenges connected with growing migration.	Adaptation via a third party	External collaboration outside of the system
Promote local regenerative agriculture	Reuse, recycle and regenerate. Reducing import and export of food and systematically encouraging agro-ecological solutions. Imported inputs and seeds all have local substitutes.	System-wide adaptation	Broad collaboration

Table B.1. Selected policy ideas developed by simulation participants matched with response typology and governance modalities.

During the debriefing session of the policy simulation, participants reflected on the policy ideas they developed during the simulation. Debriefing was structured around curated elements of the response framework, i.e., response typology and governance modalities. Because the framework was still in an earlier stage of development, the elements were not explicitly mentioned in the debrief session, as well as the proposed process for assessing response appropriateness. Stakeholders still explored policies from across the typology, analysed their governance modalities, and acknowledged how one impact can be addressed by multiple policy responses.

The response framework-based debriefing combined with the simulation experience helped workshop participants to structure the discussion around the appropriate policy responses to cascading climate impacts and to precisely identify possible points of intervention within the system. Nearly 50 stakeholders and project partners were able to discuss the proposed policy ideas using a shared, precise language. A great majority (around 90% of surveyed workshop participants) agreed that the workshop

helped them better understand the complexity of the underlying system depicted in the simulation and that they were stimulated into learning and sharing knowledge among them. More than half of the respondents mentioned that the workshop prompted them to think of the complexity of impact and response transmission systems, and of constellations of actors at different scales. Many participants also came to the conclusion that the workshop helped them “take a global view of the issues [adaptation], thinking outside the narrow lens of current organization” (Adamczak and Jarzabek, 2022).

List of supplementary material

Supplementary material 1: Full diagram of the policy simulation on food security crisis.

Supplementary material 2: List of all policy ideas (responses) generated during the simulation run.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sara Talebian: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualisation. Magnus Benzie: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. Katy Harris: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. Łukasz Jarzabek: Investigation, Writing - original draft, visualisations. Piotr Magnuszewski: Investigation, Writing - review & editing, visualisations. Noam Obermeister: Writing - review & editing, visualisations. Tim Carter: Conceptualisation, Writing - review & editing.

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